

ISic0947

I.Sicily inscription 0947

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacombs

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ἀνεπαύσατο ὁ μακαρίας
2. μνήμης · Ἰωάννιος τῆ
3. πρὸ · θ · καλ(ανδῶν) Ἰουνίων
4. μετὰ τὴν ὑπ(ατίαν) Θεοδοσίου
5. τὸ □ ις καὶ Φαύστου

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492577

EDCS 39102104

PHI 140428

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0947. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4340158>